

Application of Endochronic Theory of Viscoplasticity to Composite Materials

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ABSTRACT

It is well known that composite materials show rate sensitive mechanical behavior which, in addition, indicates that these materials have a permanent memory of the strain (or loading) path by which their present state has been attained. The recent advent of the endochronic theory developed by Valanis holds promise of describing this complicated material behavior. The theory stemmed from the premise that the time scale, with respect to which the memory of a material determines the current stress, is not the absolute time scale as measured by an ordinary clock, but by an intrinsic time scale which not only depends on the path history of deformation and deformation rate but also the constitution of the material at hand.

The constitutive equation was formulated in the frame work of the irreversible thermodynamic theory of internal variables in conjunction with the intrinsic time scale. The explicit stress-strain-time equation was derived for the small deformation under isothermal conditions which predicts quite well for various strain loading history of composite materials.

